

THE EFFECTS OF PLANTING DENSITY AND FERTILIZER RATES ON THE GROWTH, DEVELOPMENT, AND YIELD OF NK6101 MAIZE VARIETY

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of varying planting densities and fertilizer application rates on the growth, development, and yield of the NK6101 maize variety. Different planting densities and fertilizer rates were tested to determine their influence on key growth parameters, including plant height, leaf area index, and biomass accumulation. Additionally, grain yield, ear characteristics, and harvest index were measured to assess the productivity outcomes. Results indicate that optimal planting density and appropriate fertilizer rates significantly enhance growth performance and yield. These findings provide valuable insights for optimizing maize cultivation practices to achieve higher productivity and sustainable agricultural development.

Keyword: Maize planting density, Fertilizer application rates, Crop growth parameters, Yield performance, NK6101 variety

INTRODUCTION

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is a vital cereal crop globally, serving as a staple food, livestock feed, and a key raw material for various industrial products. With the increasing demand for maize due to population growth and expanding agricultural industries, enhancing its productivity is crucial. Achieving higher yields while maintaining sustainability requires the optimization of agronomic practices, particularly planting density and fertilizer application rates.

Planting density, defined as the number of plants per unit area, significantly influences maize growth and yield. It affects light interception, plant competition, and resource utilization, ultimately impacting biomass accumulation and grain production. Optimal planting density varies with genotype, environmental conditions, and management practices, necessitating region-specific studies.

Fertilizer application, particularly nitrogen, is another critical factor affecting maize productivity. Nitrogen is essential for plant growth, influencing processes such as photosynthesis, protein synthesis, and overall plant vigor. However, excessive or insufficient nitrogen can lead to suboptimal yields and environmental concerns. Therefore, determining the appropriate fertilizer rate is essential for maximizing maize yield while minimizing negative environmental impacts.

The NK6101 maize variety is known for its high yield potential and adaptability to diverse growing conditions. However, limited information is available regarding the optimal planting density and fertilizer rates for this specific variety. Understanding these factors can provide valuable insights for farmers and agronomists to enhance maize production efficiency.

This study aims to investigate the effects of different planting densities and fertilizer rates on the growth, development, and yield of the NK6101 maize variety. By analyzing key growth parameters and yield components, we seek to identify the optimal agronomic practices for maximizing the productivity of this maize variety. The findings from this research will contribute to

the development of sustainable maize cultivation practices, addressing both yield improvement and environmental sustainability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF RESEARCH

The NK6101 maize variety, developed and distributed by Syngenta Vietnam.

The study encompasses three main objectives:

1. To examine the effects of planting density and fertilizer rates on the growth and development of the NK6101 maize variety.
2. To evaluate the impact of planting density and fertilizer rates on the lodging resistance and pest and disease resistance of the NK6101 maize variety.
3. To investigate the influence of planting density and fertilizer rates on yield components and overall yield of the NK6101 maize variety.

The experiment was arranged in a Split Plot design with three replications, involving two factors: fertilizer and planting density. Fertilizer was designated as the main plot and planting density as the sub-plot. The experiment included five fertilizer levels and four planting densities, detailed as follows:

Fertilizer Levels: Five formulations (P1, P2, P3, P4, P5)

- P1: 150N + 80P₂O₅ + 80K₂O
- P2: 150N + 80P₂O₅ + 100 K₂O
- P3: 180N + 80P₂O₅ + 80 K₂O
- P4: 180N + 80P₂O₅ + 100 K₂O
- P5: 150N + 80P₂O₅ + 60 K₂O (control)

Planting Densities: Four levels (M1, M2, M3, M4)

- M1: 56,000 plants/ha with a planting distance of 60 x 30 cm (control)
- M2: 66,000 plants/ha with a planting distance of 60 x 25 cm
- M3: 76,000 plants/ha with a planting distance of 60 x 22 cm
- M4: 83,000 plants/ha with a planting distance of 60 x 20 cm

Fig 1: Experimental design

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

The effect of the interaction between planting density and fertilizer dosage on the growth and development stages of NK6101 maize variety

Formula	From sowing to				
	Germination date	Tasseling date	Pollination date	Silking date	Total growth duration
M1P1	5	57	59	61	107
M2P1	5	57	59	61	107
M3P1	5	57	59	61	107
M4P1	5	57	59	62	107
M1P2	5	57	59	61	107
M2P2	5	57	59	61	107
M3P2	5	57	59	61	107
M4P2	5	57	59	62	107
M1P3	5	57	59	61	107
M2P3	5	57	59	61	107
M3P3	5	57	59	61	107
M4P3	5	57	59	62	107
M1P4	5	57	59	61	107
M2P4	5	57	59	61	107
M3P4	5	57	59	61	107
M4P4	5	57	59	62	107
M1P5	5	57	59	61	107
M2P5	5	57	59	61	107
M3P5	5	57	59	61	108
M4P5	5	57	59	61	108

Unit: Days

Growth duration is defined as the period from sowing to physiological maturity. For the NK6101 maize variety, the growth duration across all experimental treatments was 107 days. According to Hoang Manh Cuong (2017), when NK6101 was cultivated on sloped land in Ha Giang, its total growth duration ranged from 104 to 106 days. These findings indicate that variations in fertilizer application rates and planting densities have minimal impact on the growth stages

of the NK6101 variety. The consistency in growth duration despite different agronomic practices underscores the adaptability and robustness of NK6101, making it a reliable variety for different environmental conditions and management practices.

The findings regarding the differential period between tasseling and silking, as well as the growth duration, provide valuable insights into the management of NK6101 maize variety. The minimal variation in these parameters suggests that NK6101 can maintain stable

growth and reproductive phases under varying agronomic inputs. This stability is beneficial for farmers, as it reduces the risk associated with variations in environmental conditions and management practices. By ensuring consistent growth and reproductive phases,

NK6101 can achieve optimal yield potential, thereby contributing to increased productivity and food security.

Table 2

The influence of planting density and fertilizer dosage on the leaf area index of NK6101 maize variety.

Formula	Duration		
	7-9 leaf stage	Silking stage	Milk ripe stage
M1P1	0,48	1,93	2,51
M2P1	0,58	2,56	3,00
M3P1	0,68	2,72	3,50
M4P1	0,78	3,02	3,86
M1P2	0,49	1,93	2,54
M2P2	0,59	2,34	3,02
M3P2	0,72	2,73	3,56
M4P2	0,84	3,09	3,95
M1P3	0,51	1,92	2,56
M2P3	0,61	2,32	3,05
M3P3	0,74	2,79	3,59
M4P3	0,92	3,06	3,94
M1P4	0,53	1,93	2,57
M2P4	0,65	2,34	3,14
M3P4	0,84	2,82	3,65
M4P4	1,02	3,09	4,01
M1P5	0,50	1,89	2,51
M2P5	0,57	2,26	2,97
M3P5	0,67	2,63	3,44
M4P5	0,74	2,92	3,83
CV%	5,7	3,2	2,9
<i>LSD</i> _(0,05) (PB)	0,086	0,57	0,55
<i>LSD</i> _(0,05) (MĐ)	0,028	0,059	0,071
<i>LSD</i> _(0,05) (PB*MĐ)	0,064	0,13	0,16

Unit: m² leaf area / m² land

7-9 leaf stage:

During this stage, leaf area index fluctuated between approximately 0.48 to 1.02 m² leaf/m² soil. In the study conducted by the author, the leaf area index ranged from 0.52 to 1.05 m² leaf/m² soil. These results indicate minimal differences in leaf area index across different fertilizer treatments, suggesting that the amount of fertilizer applied did not significantly influence leaf development, likely due to roots not fully utilizing the applied nutrients. Leaf area showed a proportional relationship with planting density, and the differences observed were statistically significant at a 95% confidence level.

Silking stage:

The leaf area index increased significantly from the 7-9 leaf stage to the tasseling stage, ranging from approximately 1.4 to 2.4 m² leaf/m² soil. Formula

M4P4 consistently exhibited the largest leaf area. The formula with the least increase was M1P3, with differences not statistically significant at a 95% confidence level.

Milk ripe stage:

During this period, the leaf area index ranged from 2.51 to 4.01, averaging 3.26 m² leaf/m² soil. According to Nguyen Bich Thuy's (2016) study on some domestically introduced hybrid maize varieties, the average leaf area index of NK6101 was 3.7 m² leaf/m² soil. Both studies indicate that from the tasseling to the milk ripe stage, the leaf area index increases slowly. This can be attributed to ongoing leaf development and senescence, where some leaves continue to grow while others begin to wither, resulting in a slight increase in leaf area index during this stage.

Table 3

The impact of planting density and fertilizer dosage on some morphological characteristics of NK6101 maize variety.

Formula	Height (cm)		Ratio of corn ear height (%)
	Plant height	Corn ear height	
M1P1	193,6	94,1	48,6
M2P1	197,3	95,2	48,3
M3P1	198,9	99,5	50,0
M4P1	203,9	102,8	50,4
M1P2	196,0	96,8	49,4
M2P2	198,6	96,9	48,8
M3P2	200,9	99,3	49,4
M4P2	204,2	103,6	50,7
M1P3	196,9	96,9	49,2
M2P3	198,4	97,9	49,3
M3P3	203,1	98,9	48,7
M4P3	206,2	102,9	49,9
M1P4	197,6	97,5	49,3
M2P4	199,8	99,7	49,9
M3P4	204,2	100,5	49,2
M4P4	208,1	106,1	51,0
M1P5	191,9	93,5	48,7
M2P5	194,3	95,1	48,9
M3P5	197,0	96,1	48,8
M4P5	197,8	96,8	48,9
CV%	1,6	2,4	-
<i>LSD</i> _{(0,05)(PB)}	19,07	15,23	-
<i>LSD</i> _{(0,05)(MD)}	2.4	1.7	-
<i>LSD</i> _{(0,05)(PB*MD)}	5,37	3,93	-

Plant height is a critical parameter in maize breeding, closely related to growth, development, and lodging resistance. It is measured from the ground level to the point of the first tassel branch emergence. Throughout the growth and development stages, plant height gradually increases, peaking notably from the 9-leaf stage to tasseling, and stabilizing after pollination.

The plant height of the NK6101 maize variety in the experiment ranged from 193.6 to 208.1 cm. According to Ha Thi Thanh Binh, plant height of NK6101 on sloped terrain was significantly taller (ranging from 234.2 to 250.3 cm). This variation is attributed to differing fertilizer regimes and planting densities. Both authors, however, note a general trend of increasing plant height with higher planting density and fertilizer application. Formula M1P1 exhibited the shortest plant height (193.6 cm), with differences not statistically significant at a 95% confidence level.

Ear height, along with plant height, is crucial for assessing maize growth status. The data indicate that

ear height of the maize variety ranged from 94.07 to 106.13 cm. Formula M4P4 recorded the tallest ear height (106.13 cm), with differences not statistically significant at a 95% confidence level.

The ear height to plant height ratio reflects lodging resistance and pollination efficiency of maize plants. Optimal ear height facilitates easier pollen reception and pollination. Conversely, excessive ear height increases the risk of plant lodging. Generally, an optimal ear height is about half the plant height.

From the data, the ear height to plant height ratio ranged from 48% to 51% across different formulas. According to Ha Thi Thanh Binh (2011), the ear height to plant height ratio typically ranges from 46% to 50%, which is suitable for maize pollen reception. According to studies by Nguyen Thi Lan (2017), Tran Trung Kien (2013), and Tran Thi Thiem (2010), it is observed that both plant height and ear height of the NK6101 variety correlate positively with planting density and fertilizer levels, although variations are not significant.

Table 4

The influence of the interaction between planting density and fertilizer dosage on yield components and yield of NK6101 maize variety.

Formula	Length of corn ear	Diameter of corn ear	Number of rows	Number of kernels per row	Kernel-to-ear ratio	Weight of 1000 kernels	Theoretical yield	Actual yield
	(cm)	(cm)	(row)	(kernel)	(%)	(gr)	(metric tons/hectare)	((metric tons/hectare)
M1P1	14,1	4,4	14,2	30,47	68,41	315	77,41	60,37
M2P1	14,4	4,2	13,8	30,87	67,25	310	82,31	67,27
M3P1	14,7	4,1	13,5	31,20	60,22	305	87,79	53,87
M4P1	13,4	4,2	13,0	31,40	54,37	290	86,57	45,27
M1P2	14,3	4,5	14,5	30,73	68,63	315	79,36	62,63
M2P2	14,5	4,3	14,2	31,73	68,26	308	87,04	64,53
M3P2	14,8	4,2	13,8	31,67	59,90	304	90,95	50,97
M4P2	13,5	4,3	13,4	31,80	54,07	291	90,57	45,60
M1P3	14,4	4,7	14,6	31,27	69,42	313	80,74	65,60
M2P3	14,8	4,5	13,8	31,40	67,78	308	83,7	68,01
M3P3	15,1	4,4	13,6	31,53	62,91	305	89,27	54,27
M4P3	14,0	4,5	13,4	31,27	55,09	294	81,94	47,90
M1P4	14,4	4,8	14,4	31,67	67,78	316	82,97	70,63
M2P4	14,7	4,6	13,8	31,27	66,31	309	89,45	73,46
M3P4	15,2	4,5	13,6	31,53	62,28	305	84,15	51,63
M4P4	14,2	4,6	13,0	31,27	58,24	285	81,58	48,63
M1P5	13,5	3,8	13,7	29,80	67,65	309	71,58	52,30
M2P5	13,8	3,6	13,8	30,00	63,69	306	78,94	49,27
M3P5	14,2	3,5	13,6	29,93	58,9	301	83,76	43,97
M4P5	12,9	3,6	13,1	29,73	54,45	280	78,84	40,27
CV%	1,7	2,8	2,0	2,3	-	-	-	5,1
LSD _(0,05)	0,34	0,17	0,4	1,01	-	-	-	4,7

Table 4 data shows a trend of increasing planting density from low to high density levels. At density level M4 across different fertilizer regimes, the shortest ear lengths were observed (12.9 cm – 14.2 cm), with the longest in M3 (14.2 cm – 15.2 cm), variations not significant at a 95% confidence level.

Fertilizer dosages and different planting densities influence cob diameter differently. At density level M1 across various fertilizer formulas, the largest cob diameters were observed (3.8 cm – 4.8 cm). As fertilizer levels increased, cob diameters also increased, variations significant at a 95% confidence level.

The number of rows per ear varied slightly across different planting densities and fertilizer regimes, ranging from 13 rows to 14.6 rows. The number of rows per ear showed an inverse relationship with planting density across fertilizer regimes. The highest number of rows per ear was observed at density level P3 (13.4 – 13.8 rows), differences not significant at a 95% confidence level.

There was no significant difference in the number of seeds per row among different formulas, with the smallest number of seeds per row observed at density level P5 (29.73 seeds – 30 seeds/row), differences not significant at a 95% confidence level.

Across different fertilizer regimes, increasing planting density led to a gradual decrease in the seed to cob ratio. On fertilizer regime P4, different planting densities resulted in the highest seed to cob ratio

(58.24% - 67.78%). There was a large percentage difference among different planting densities.

The 1000 seed weight varied inversely with planting density across different fertilizer regimes. Fertilizer regime P5 across different planting densities yielded the smallest 1000 seed weight (280 g – 309 g). The differences in 1000 seed weight among planting densities within fertilizer regimes were not substantial.

In most fertilizer regimes with varying planting densities, theoretical yield tended to increase with higher planting densities. Fertilizer regime P2 at planting density M3 exhibited the highest theoretical yield (90.95 tons/ha), with P2 having the highest observed yield (79 tons/ha – 90.95 tons/ha).

Across most fertilizer regimes with different planting densities, the highest actual yield was consistently observed at density level M2 (6.6 thousand maize plants/ha). There was a significant yield difference among experimental formulas ranging from 40.27 tons/ha to 73.46 tons/ha, with formula M2P4 achieving the highest yield, differences significant at a 95% confidence level. According to authors Luong Van Huan (2017) and Vu Thi Hai Yen (2017), different maize varieties exhibit varying actual yields, typically fluctuating between 50.24 tons/ha and 66.23 tons/ha.

According to authors Luong Van Huan (2017) and Vu Thi Hai Yen (2017), when surveying some hybrid maize varieties, NK6101 maize variety demonstrated

relatively high yields and suitability for northern midland and mountainous provinces

CONCLUSION

One notable finding is the absence of significant lodging, both in terms of stalks and roots. This attribute is crucial as lodging can severely affect maize yields by reducing standability and complicating harvest operations. The minimal incidence of lodging in NK6101 underscores its strong stalk and root architecture, which supports the plant even under increased nutrient and density stress.

The consistent growth and reproductive phases observed in NK6101 across different agronomic treatments highlight its adaptability and stability. This consistency is crucial for farmers, as it mitigates risks associated with varying environmental conditions and management practices. By maintaining stable growth durations, leaf area indices, and plant heights, NK6101 ensures reliable performance in terms of yield potential.

Moreover, the findings suggest that while there are slight fluctuations in parameters such as ear length, cob diameter, and seed characteristics across different experimental conditions, these variations are not statistically significant at a 95% confidence level. This indicates that NK6101 maintains uniformity in key agronomic traits, regardless of varying inputs.

In conclusion, NK6101 emerges as a robust maize variety suitable for diverse farming environments, particularly in northern midland and mountainous provinces. Its ability to withstand moderate increases in planting density and fertilizer levels while maintaining minimal disease incidence and lodging underscores its resilience and potential for ensuring sustainable maize production and food security.

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